

TERMINOLOGY AND FIELDS OF APPLICATION OF LANDSCAPE TERMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Abstract.

the article describes the use of terminology, a comparative analysis of landscape terms in Uzbek and English, and the opinions of linguists regarding the field of use.

Key words.

article, term, English, Russian, Uzbek, linguistics, application, field, linguistics.

The concepts of "terminal" and "terminology" have many definitions proposed by English, Russian, Uzbek and foreign linguists. Agreeing with the opinion of V.M. Leychik, we emphasize that "term (from Latin terminus - limit, border) is a word or phrase that expresses the concept of a special field of knowledge or activity" and "terminology (from term and term) Greek logos - word, education) - a set of terms denoting a set of terms of any special field of knowledge or activity (for example, linguistics), as well as any natural language (for example, English terminology)" [3, p. 558] Under consideration the study of language materials shows that terms are not always unambiguous, compact and context-independent. In our opinion, they remain context-independent when they are at the highest stage of their development, i.e. . when the form and content of the term do not contradict each other, and this is achieved by special modeling of the terms of one field by a single structural-semantic community. It should also be noted that the terms are characteristic of the main scientific method, i.e. they are used in scientific works, research , is more widely used in industrial and general language dictionaries, etc. In this regard, it is worth noting that despite the emergence and formation of terms from ordinary lexical units, the latter become the owner of new functions. The study of the literature on the term and terminology led to the fact that the lexical unit, from the moment it became a term, acquired a dual function. Any term is used as a simple, everyday word until it acquires a specific character, and in such cases it has only a nominative character, while the same simple word, when it becomes a term, immediately acquires the quality of definiteness. Kinship terms in English, Russian and Uzbek languages have deep roots and a rich

historical past. However, in order to prevent all contradictory phenomena in this complex phenomenon, a deep study of the complex mechanism of the creation of terms in the history of language and ways of their wider application is required. The comparative study of languages provides valuable material for their general theory, helps to determine the place of each in the system of world languages. It is also used to solve such an important problem as the laws of development and interaction of languages. The great attention of linguists to the comparative typological study of different types of languages, which has increased recently, has been justified. This is a unique response to the ever-increasing development of the globalization process in all aspects of the material and spiritual life of the world community. Translation issues, information service, tasks of creating various dictionaries and references, improvement of methods. teaching the mother tongue is one of the urgent tasks facing comparative typology. It is this aspect that prompted us to choose kinship terms in English, Russian and Uzbek languages as the object of study. It should be noted right away that the typological consideration of the analyzed languages is not the main task before us, a simpler task is set - to compare and contrast the personal names of these languages with a specific lexical layer. In this section, we will consider some features of the speech activity of English common nouns with personal meaning. In the speech, the words used as an address are selected as material, i.e. appeals. It is intended to determine the pragmatic, that is, the semantic status of appellatives according to their ability to describe the communicative situation and the communicants themselves. In this regard, a question arises about the relationship between word semantics and linguistic pragmatics. There are two points of view on this issue: some linguists understand the meaning of a sign only as a phenomenon of linguistic order, while pragmatics is considered as a phenomenon of extralinguistic level. The second point of view is characterized by the refusal to understand the meaning of the word as defining only what constitutes the narrowest concept of the object in the linguistic sign. In the works of recent years, the meaning of the word is understood unusually broadly - as universal and even individual (subjective) knowledge on the subject, social and personal experience. Within this understanding of meaning, it seems reasonable to consider that pragmatics is an aspect of semantics, and the actual pragmatic side of word meaning is information about the communicants and the conditions for the flow of a particular word. . The view that the process of acquiring foreign words takes place in all languages also corresponds to terminology. "In all languages, to express a new concept, either a ready-made term from another language is adopted, or a word or term existing in this language is

used, or a new term is created," S. Akobirov said. Acquisition as a derivational process is well studied in linguistics. Russian linguist L.P. Krisin states that it is usually considered as a transition of elements of one language to another language system as a result of long-term contacts between two languages. As a result of combining words and morphemes borrowed from Arabic and Persian with lexemes from Russian and other European languages, complex word combinations are formed: study of the laws of nature, natural objects, natural system, world ocean, air pool, geographical environment, natural resources, natural landscape, terrain, etc. Russian and English ecological terms have been directly borrowed from Uzbek and Karakalpak languages: in Russian, the term benthos is borrowed from Greek and means ventos, in English, benthos - in Uzbek and Karakalpak languages, benthos means a collection of organisms that live at the bottom of water bodies. Similar terms include biogeocenosis - stable earth ecosystem; biome is usually used to mean ecosystems that are similar to the composition of plants located in natural-climatic regions. In the formation and enrichment of environmental terms in English, terms borrowed from Greek, Latin, German and French have a special place. Ecology (Greek oikos - housing, logos - science) as environmental terms that have entered the Russian language from English - ecology; biology (Greek bios - haèt, logos - science) - biology; reservoir (French reservoir - reservoir, pool, reservoir) reservoir, reservoir; acclimatization (lat. ad-k, grer. klimatos - kiya) acclimatization; algology (Lat. algalogy - ucheniye) - algology, antagonism (Greek antagonism - fight, fight) - antagonism, population (Lat. population - people) and others. A technology whose nature of impact on nature depends on the production relations of society. Apparently, he was the first to draw attention to the need to distinguish "anthropogenic landscapes", determine the boundaries of the landscape and study the history of development. The foundations of the theory of landscape studies were created in the fundamental work "Landscape and Geographical Zones of the USSR" (Berg, 1931). Here, in the introduction, the doctrine of landscape was presented for the first time and the foundations of genetic landscape science were created. In particular, he proposed to consider the landscape as the main unit in the science of geography and gave the following definition to the studied object: "Geographical landscape is such a collection or grouping of things and phenomena of the relief of specific characteristics, interdependence. climate, waters, soil and vegetation cover and animal life, as well as human activity, are usually combined into a single harmonious whole that repeats itself in a certain area of the Earth" (1931, p. 5). Landscape to the study of the anthropogenic factor in the formation of landscapes L. G. Ramonsky (1935, 1938) is one of the founders of the theory of

morphology. Emphasizing that the object of research should be not only natural, but man-made and newly created cultural landscapes, Ramensky was the first to show the connection of anthropogenic landscapes with natural landscapes, their natural He expressed the cultural changes of the land type as temporary changes of the area under the influence of culture, and the most important characteristic of cultural changes is their practical restoration, if a certain cultural when a change occurs under the influence of a regime, it turns into another or returns to the original, local type.

REFERENCES:

1. Usmanova, S. (2022). An analysis of" assimilation" of landscape terms. Eurasian Scientific Herald, 14, 32-36.
2. Usmanova, S. (2022). Comparative analysis of landscape terms in Uzbek and English and usage of terms. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 14, 1-3.
3. Shaxnoza, U. (2022). Comparative Study of Cosmonims (Sun, Moon...) In Uzbek and English. Eurasian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, 7, 72-75.
4. Shaxnoza, U. (2022). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILIDA LANDSHAFT SO'ZLARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI VA FRAZEALOGIYA. Uzbek Scholar Journal, 4, 53-55.
5. Usmonova, S. (2023). MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN PRIMARY CLASSES. Бюллетень студентов нового Узбекистана, 1(3), 27-29.
6. Abdurakhmonov, V. (2022). FUNCTIONAL SPECIFICITY OF ALTERNATIVE INTERROGATIVE SENTENCES. Oriental Journal of Social Sciences, 2(03), 82-87.
7. Ravshanovna, G. N. (2022, April). THE STUDY OF THE MEANING OF THE WORD TOLERANCE IN OTHER LANGUAGES. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-9).